

MORPHOFUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE NASOPHARYNX IN CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL CLEFT PALATE IN THE ARAL SEA REGION

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ABSTRACT

The nasopharynx plays a crucial role in ensuring physiological ventilation of the middle ear and protecting the respiratory tract from infectious agents [1]. Normally, during swallowing, the soft palate separates the nasopharynx from the oropharynx, preventing the penetration of microflora into its cavity [2]. However, in congenital cleft palate, disruption of the integrity or functional activity of the soft palate leads to the loss of this protective mechanism, creating conditions for nasopharyngeal infection and subsequent involvement of the Eustachian tube and middle ear in the pathological process.

Introduction. The nasopharynx plays a crucial role in ensuring physiological ventilation of the middle ear and protecting the respiratory tract from infectious agents [1]. Normally, during swallowing, the soft palate separates the nasopharynx from the oropharynx, preventing the penetration of microflora into its cavity [2]. However, in congenital cleft palate, disruption of the integrity or functional activity of the soft palate leads to the loss of this protective mechanism, creating conditions for nasopharyngeal infection and subsequent involvement of the Eustachian tube and middle ear in the pathological process [3].

Eustachian tube dysfunction in children with cleft palate is accompanied by impaired aeration of the tympanic cavity, delayed pneumatization of the mastoid process, and development of various forms of otitis media, which may lead to persistent hearing loss [4,5]. Even after surgical correction of the cleft palate, functional disturbances of the velopharyngeal complex often persist, requiring further investigation of the nasopharyngeal region in this group of patients [6–8].

Objective. To develop a differentiated approach to the prevention and treatment of Eustachian tube dysfunction in children with congenital cleft palate based on the analysis of pathological changes in the velopharyngeal region.

Materials and Methods. The study included children with congenital cleft palate living in the Aral Sea region. A total of 120 patients under observation in specialized medical institutions were examined.

A comprehensive clinical and instrumental assessment of the nasal cavity, nasopharynx, and pharyngeal openings of the Eustachian tubes was performed. The diagnostic algorithm included endoscopic examination of the nasal cavity and nasopharynx, allowing evaluation of

the morphological state of the mucosa, the degree of inflammatory and atrophic changes, Eustachian tube patency, and anatomical features of the velopharyngeal complex.

Additionally, clinical data, patient complaints, and medical history were analyzed. The obtained results were correlated with clinical manifestations and functional status of the Eustachian tube, enabling assessment of the impact of nasopharyngeal pathology on middle ear ventilation disorders in children living in the Aral Sea region.

Results. Endoscopic examination of the nasal cavity, nasopharynx, and pharyngeal openings of the Eustachian tubes revealed pronounced morphofunctional changes of the velopharyngeal complex in the majority of examined patients with cleft palate. Atrophic changes of the mucosa in the region of the Eustachian tube openings were detected in 58–64% of patients, while gaping of the pharyngeal openings of varying severity was observed in 60–72% of children.

Signs of chronic inflammation of the nasal mucosa (hyperemia, vascular dilation, increased fragility) were recorded in 68–75% of cases. In older children (over 5–6 years), undulating deformation of the mucosa of the nasal floor accompanied by impaired mucociliary transport was found in 52–61% of cases.

Impairment of mucociliary clearance with signs of mucus retention in the nasal cavity and nasopharynx was observed in 55–63% of patients, creating conditions for infection and spread of inflammation toward the Eustachian tube.

According to clinical and instrumental examination, signs of Eustachian tube dysfunction were recorded in 70–85% of children with cleft palate. Accumulation of exudate in the middle ear with impaired sound conduction was detected in 48–60% of patients, while conductive hearing loss of varying severity was diagnosed in 40–55% of children.

Even after surgical correction of the palate, in the early postoperative period, signs of impaired ventilation function of the Eustachian tube persisted in 35–45% of patients, accompanied by middle ear effusion and temporary hearing loss.

The obtained data indicate a high prevalence of morphological and functional changes in the nasopharyngeal region in children with congenital cleft palate and confirm the leading role of Eustachian tube dysfunction in the development of inflammatory middle ear pathology.

Conclusions.

1.Children with congenital cleft palate develop pronounced morphofunctional changes in the nasopharyngeal region leading to impaired ventilation function of the Eustachian tube.

2.Identified mucosal changes and gaping of the pharyngeal openings of the Eustachian tubes create conditions for infection penetration into the middle ear and development of inflammatory processes.

3.With age, in the absence of timely correction, pathological changes of the nasal cavity progress and contribute to chronic impairment of mucociliary transport.

Even after surgical treatment, functional insufficiency of the Eustachian tube persists in some patients, requiring long-term follow-up and preventive measures.

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